

TRENDS IN SLEEP PATTERNS AMONG CZECH ADOLESCENTS AND THEIR CURRENT CORRELATES OF LATE BEDTIMES AND SOCIAL JET LAG: HBSC STUDY 2014–2022

Erik Sigmund¹, Dagmar Sigmundová¹, Jaroslava Voráčová¹, Jana Fürstová², Michal Kalman², Inese Gobija^{3,4}, Petr Baďura²

¹Faculty of Physical Culture, Institute of Active Lifestyle, Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic

²Sts Cyril and Methodius Faculty of Theology, Olomouc University Social Health Institute, Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic

³Institute of Public Health, Riga Stradiņš University, Riga, Latvia

⁴Department of Education and Research, Children's Clinical University Hospital, Riga, Latvia

SUMMARY

Objectives: Sleep is vital for maintaining the health and wellbeing of people of all ages. However, for adolescents, sufficient sleep of adequate duration and quality is critical for profound mental, physical, social, and emotional development. This study aimed to describe trends in sleep duration and late bedtime during school and non-school days in representative cohorts of 11-, 13-, and 15-year-old adolescents from Czechia from 2014 to 2022, and to examine the current associations between late bedtimes/social jet lag and wellbeing indicators among adolescents in 2022.

Methods: The analysed sample of 42,101 adolescents aged 10.5–16.5 years was drawn from three nationally representative cohorts of Czech schoolchildren from the last three cycles of the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children study, conducted between 2014 and 2022.

Results: Mean sleep duration (hours:minutes) on school and non-school days significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased for both boys (school days: 8:19₂₀₁₄ → 7:59₂₀₂₂; non-school days: 9:36₂₀₁₈ → 9:23₂₀₂₂) and girls (school days: 8:20₂₀₁₄ → 7:55₂₀₂₂; non-school days: 9:58₂₀₁₈ → 9:41₂₀₂₂) between 2014/2018 and 2022, while the prevalence of insufficient sleep significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased over the same period (boys school days: 35.4%₂₀₁₄ → 49.2%₂₀₂₂, boys non-school days: 14.9%₂₀₁₈ → 18.0%₂₀₂₂; girls school days: 35.1%₂₀₁₄ → 51.7%₂₀₂₂, girls non-school days: 9.8%₂₀₁₈ → 13.3%₂₀₂₂). Adolescents with late bedtimes or social jet lag (>2 hours) had significantly higher odds ($p < 0.001$) of skipping breakfast daily, drinking energy drinks daily, being drunk at least twice in their lifetime, experiencing reduced psychological wellbeing and low life satisfaction, reporting irritability, and problematic social media use and internet gaming than those with earlier bedtimes or without social jet lag.

Conclusions: It is highly desirable that families, in close cooperation with schools and professional representatives, make efforts to ensure adherence to the recommended length and quality of sleep, as the trend results indicate worsening sleep patterns, deepening social jet lag, and a disturbing increase in adolescent risk behaviours and health complaints related to insufficient sleep.

Key words: sleep, trends, bedtime, social jet lag, school days, adolescents

Address for correspondence: E. Sigmund, Faculty of Physical Culture, Institute of Active Lifestyle, Palacký University Olomouc, Třída Míru 671/117, 771 11 Olomouc, Czech Republic. E-mail: erik.sigmund@upol.cz

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INTRODUCTION

Sufficient, regular, and high-quality sleep is essential for children's and adolescents' physical, emotional and cognitive health and wellbeing (1). Sleep is also an important physiological state for the recovery, consolidation and generalisation of new learning (2). Today's adolescents encounter challenges that reduce the amount of sleep they receive regularly. Relevant international analyses of adolescent sleep patterns addressing sleep duration, bedtimes, and wake-up times either do not include data on Czech adolescents (3, 4) or are outdated, containing data only up to 2018

(5, 6). The latest available findings show that Czech adolescents aged 11–15 rank among their peers from Poland, Lithuania, Greece, Estonia, and Slovenia as having the shortest average sleep duration on school days (8:13 hours) and non-school days (9:38 hours) (5). In addition, Czech adolescents are comparable to those from Portugal in showing the most significant differences in sleep duration on school days between active and inactive social media users (6). Furthermore, 11–15-year-old adolescents from all 24 European countries and Canada surveyed were found to have significantly shorter sleep times on school days than on non-school days (5), and a widening gap in sleep time between

school and non-school days was observed among problematic adolescent social media users (6). Insufficient sleep on school days (<9 hours for children aged 6–13 years and <8 hours for adolescents aged 14–17 years) (7, 8) is primarily caused by late bedtimes, as wake-up times are strictly constrained by school schedules, with lessons in Czechia typically starting at 8 a.m.

From a health perspective, consistent sleep throughout the week is essential. Weekend ‘catch-up’ sleep to compensate for deficits accumulated during school days may be related to a phenomenon called ‘social jet lag’. Young people begin to experience its consequences when their sleep schedule (bedtime and wake-up times) on school days differs significantly from that on days off. Once the difference between sleep duration on non-school and school days exceeds 2 hours, significant health risks become a concern (9). Social jet lag greater than 2 hours was significantly associated with insomnia severity, hyperactivity, conduct problems, excessive daytime sleepiness, and overall behavioural problems in 11–19-year-old adolescents from Hong Kong (10), and with depression in 15-year-old northern European Russian adolescent girls (11).

Shortened sleep duration (or late bedtimes) and social jet lag are associated with health complaints (12, 13), sleep difficulties (14), and risk behaviours (6, 10) in adolescents. However, in representative samples of Czech adolescents, the relationships between indicators of wellbeing (health complaints, sleep difficulties, or risk behaviours) and late bedtimes are not sufficiently clarified (15), nor are the latest findings on the sleep patterns of Czech adolescents. Therefore, the aim of the present study is to complement the insufficient or fragmented information on the sleep patterns of Czech adolescents aged 11–15 years between 2014 and 2022, with a focus on adolescent wellbeing indicators. The primary objective of the study was to describe trends and differences in sleep duration and late bedtimes during school and non-school days among Czech adolescents, taking into account gender and age cohort. A secondary objective was to examine the most current relationships between late bedtimes and social jet lag with adolescent wellbeing indicators (health complaints, sleep difficulties or risk behaviours) in 2022.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study and Participants

The current analyses are based on three waves of data collection from Czech adolescents aged 11–15 years in 2014, 2018 and

2022, which are methodologically covered by the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC) study. The HBSC study is an international repeated cross-sectional survey to monitor health and wellbeing of adolescents in Europe, Canada and Central Asia in collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO). The survey collects data every 4 years from a representative cohort of 11-, 13- and 15-year-old schoolchildren, following a standardised methodological protocol (16, 17). The HBSC study uses stratified random cluster sampling, with schools as the primary sampling units. Participants provide self-reported data by anonymously and voluntarily completing a questionnaire in schools under the supervision of researchers. The parents/guardians of the adolescents were informed about the study through the school management and had the option to opt their children out if they did not consent to participation. Before completing the questionnaire, the participants confirmed their informed consent to participation in the research. The Institutional Ethics Committee for Research of the Faculty of Physical Culture of Palacký University Olomouc approved the design of the cross-sectional study, the course of preparation and implementation of the research and the opt-out method of collecting parental consent and data processing for data collection in 2014 (2018 and 2022) in March 2013 under No. 17/2013 (on 4 March 2016 under No. 9/2016 and on 10 October 2020 under No. 65/2020). The final data set comprised 42,101 adolescents (girls: $n=7,156$ in 2014; $6,569$ in 2018; $7,193$ in 2022; boys: $n=6,980$ in 2014; $6,808$ in 2018; $7,395$ in 2022), aged from 10.5 to 16.5 years, all of whom provided valid and complete data on sleep-related variables (Table 1).

Sleep Patterns

Sleep time was calculated from the adolescents’ self-reported bedtime and wake-up times on school days and non-school days separately. The self-reported sleep time options ranged in half-hour intervals from ‘no later than 9:00 p.m.’ to ‘2:00 a.m. or later’ for school days and ‘no later than 9:00 p.m.’ to ‘4:00 a.m. or later’ for non-school days. The response scale for wake-up times contained categories ranging in half-hour intervals from ‘no later than 5 a.m.’ to ‘8 a.m. or later’ for school days and ‘no later than 7 a.m.’ to ‘2 p.m. or later’ for non-school days (18). Finally, sleep time was calculated as the difference between bedtime and wake-up time, separately for school and non-school days. The HBSC sleep-time related questions demonstrate substantial reliability (ICC = 0.75/0.64 for bedtime on school days/non-school days; ICC = 0.77 for waking up on school days), and almost perfect reliability (ICC = 0.83) for the waking up on non-school days

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of the samples, HBSC study, Czechia 2014–2022^a

Age category ^b	2014		2018		2022	
	Boys $n=6,980$ (%)	Girls $n=7,156$ (%)	Boys $n=6,808$ (%)	Girls $n=6,569$ (%)	Boys $n=7,395$ (%)	Girls $n=7,193$ (%)
11 years	31.8	32.1	32.4	33.1	29.2	30.3
13 years	34.4	34.4	34.8	34.8	33.1	32.3
15 years	33.8	33.5	32.8	32.1	37.7	37.4

^aWeights for strata (number of pupils/students in given grades in each region of Czechia) were applied; ^b11 years (13 years and 15 years) includes adolescents in the age range 10.5–12.49 years (12.50–14.49 years and 14.50–16.49 years)

item (19). Moderate to strong criterion validity and the strong reliability of a self-reported sleep duration questionnaire have been repeatedly demonstrated in adolescents (20). Social jet lag was estimated by calculating the difference in bedtime between school days and non-school days for all participants, regardless of gender and age category (9, 21). Considering the accuracy of bedtime estimation and the established associations with health complaints and behavioural problems (10, 11), the threshold of social jet lag was set at a 2-hour difference between sleep duration on school days and non-school days. Cut-off points for late bedtimes were defined as after 23:00 on school days and after 00:00 on non-school days, in line with a study using a similar methodological design (14). While questions on bedtime and wake-up time on school days have been part of the Czech HBSC questionnaire since 2014, questions on bedtime/wake-up time on non-school days were only included in the HBSC questionnaire in 2018.

Socio-demographic Covariates and Wellbeing Indicators

Socio-demographic and wellbeing indicators were selected from the HBSC study based on their plausible connection to the sleep patterns. Socio-demographic variables (gender, school grade, socioeconomic status) were listed along with their categorisation in the introductory methodological article. High life satisfaction was dichotomized by the Mazur et al. study (22) as follows: score ≥ 9 on Cantril Scale with values 0–10. Indicators of poor wellbeing included risk of reduced psychological wellbeing, defined as a standardised score of ≤ 28 on the WHO-5 wellbeing index (23); frequent feelings of loneliness, specifically feeling lonely most of the time or always; and health complaints – such as headaches, irritability, low mood, or nervousness – experienced at least once per week. Risk behaviours assessed in the study included daily skipping of breakfast, daily consumption of energy drinks, regular cigarette smoking, recurrent drunkenness (defined as being intoxicated on two or more occasions over the lifetime), problematic internet gaming (defined as meeting at least five criteria for addiction-like gaming behaviour) (24), and problematic social media use (SMU), defined as meeting at least six criteria for addiction-like SMU, irrespective of usage intensity (25, 26).

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

After the raw data from the HBSC questionnaires for all school classes had been received, all processing and subsequent statistical processing was conducted in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows v. 28 software (IBM Corp. Released 2021. Armonk, NY, USA). Given the study aims, checks for nonsensical and incorrect responses or incomplete questionnaire completion were performed identically for the 2014, 2018 and 2022 datasets in accordance with the HBSC study methodological protocol (16, 17). Descriptive characteristics are presented as means (Fig. 1) and percentages (Fig. 2) with respect to the distribution of variables separately for boys and girls in each age category. The Pearson chi-square (χ^2) test was repeatedly used to test for differences in mean sleep duration (or late bedtime) of adolescents between 2022 and 2014 for school days (2022 and 2018 for non-school days), separately for girls and boys, as well

as in separate cohorts of 11-year-old, 13-year-old and 15-year-old adolescents. A series of multivariate logistic regression analyses were used to reveal correlations of late bedtimes on school/non-school days (or social jet lag) controlled for gender, school grade, and family socioeconomic status using the 2022 data. The results of the logistic regression analyses are expressed using odds ratios (ORs). Due to multiple testing, the alpha significance level was set at < 0.001 .

RESULTS

Mean sleep times (hours:minutes) on school and non-school days in the monitored period significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased for both boys (school days 8:19₂₀₁₄ → 7:59₂₀₂₂; non-school days 9:36₂₀₁₈ → 9:23₂₀₂₂) and girls (school days 8:20₂₀₁₄ → 7:55₂₀₂₂; non-school days 9:58₂₀₁₈ → 9:41₂₀₂₂). The decline in sleep duration was observed in all age cohorts of adolescents studied. Between 2018 and 2022, it was more pronounced in girls than in boys on school days (Fig. 1). On non-school days, the most notable reduction in sleep duration between 2018 and 2022 was evident for 11-year-old girls (–22 minutes) and 11-year-old boys (–18 minutes) (Fig. 1).

A more than two-hour difference in sleep duration between non-school days and schooldays was found in 37% of 11-year-olds, 51% of 13-year-olds and 55% of 15-year-old adolescents. Overall weekend catch-up sleep was more common among girls than boys, as 53.3% of girls and 42.4% of boys exceeded the two-hour threshold between sleep duration on non-school days and schooldays.

On school days, the most pronounced absolute increases in late bedtimes between 2014 and 2022 were observed in the cohorts of 13-year-old (boys +11.9 percentage points (pp) and girls +13.3 pp, $p < 0.001$ χ^2 test) and 15-year-old adolescents (boys +13.5 pp and girls +13.2 pp, $p < 0.001$ χ^2 test). On non-school days, the highest increase in late bedtime between 2018 and 2022 was seen in the cohort of 11-year-old adolescents (boys +3.8 pp, $p < 0.00365$ χ^2 test, girls +5.2 pp, $p < 0.001$ χ^2 test) (Fig. 2).

Regression analyses from the 2022 data showed that adolescents with later bedtimes ($> 23:00/0:00$ hours on school/non-school days) had significantly higher odds ($p < 0.001$) of skipping breakfast every day, drinking energy drinks daily, smoking, being drunk at least twice in their lifetime, experiencing depressive states, loneliness, at least weekly headaches, irritability, low

Fig. 1. Trends in average sleep duration (hours:minutes) among Czech adolescents between 2018 and 2022.

Table 2. Current sleep patterns in association with adolescent wellbeing indicators in 2022^a

	Risk of reduced psychological wellbeing	High life satisfaction	Feelings of loneliness	Headaches at least weekly	Irritability at least weekly	Feeling low at least weekly	Nervousness at least weekly	Non-skipping breakfast every day	Drinking energy drinks daily	Smoking weekly	Drunkenness (≥2 times)	Problematic internet gaming disorder (≥5 signs present)	Problematic social media use (≥6 signs present)
Bedtime – SCHD													
>23:00 hour vs. earlier bedtime	2.29 (2.06–2.55)	0.57 (0.53–0.62)	2.46 (2.23–2.71)	2.12 (1.91–2.34)	2.15 (1.98–2.33)	2.27 (2.07–2.48)	1.91 (1.76–2.07)	0.30 (0.27–0.33)	5.62 (4.39–7.18)	3.68 (2.98–4.54)	2.96 (2.59–3.37)	2.46 (2.14–2.82)	2.74 (2.38–3.16)
Bedtime – non-SCHD													
>0:00 hour vs. earlier bedtime OR (95% CI) ^b	2.21 (1.99–2.45)	0.65 (0.60–0.70)	2.22 (2.02–2.43)	2.14 (1.94–2.36)	2.05 (1.90–2.21)	2.06 (1.89–2.25)	1.81 (1.68–1.95)	0.33 (0.30–0.35)	8.98 (6.56–12.34)	5.91 (4.54–7.70)	3.85 (3.33–4.45)	2.66 (2.32–3.05)	2.61 (2.27–3.00)
Social jet lag													
>2 hours difference vs. <30 minutes difference in sleep duration between SCHD and non-SCHD OR (95% CI) ^b	1.45 (1.21–1.74)	0.89 (0.79–1.00)	1.19 (1.02–1.39)	1.18 (1.00–1.38)	1.24 (1.10–1.40)	1.18 (1.02–1.36)	1.21 (1.07–1.36)	0.77 (0.69–0.86)	1.81 (1.25–2.63)	1.41 (1.00–1.97)	1.62 (1.28–2.04)	1.40 (1.14–1.73)	1.67 (1.30–2.13)

^aRegression analyses; OR – odds ratio; CI – confidence interval; ^bcontrolled for gender, school grade and socioeconomic status of families; SCHD – schooldays; non-SCHD – non-school days; *bold are expressed p<0.001; late bedtime at schooldays (> 23:00 hour) and non-school days (> 0:00 hour)

Fig. 2. Changes in the prevalence of late bedtime among Czech adolescents on school and non-school days between 2014 and 2022.

mood, and nervousness compared to those with earlier bedtimes (Table 2). Adolescents with social jet lag (>2 hours) also had significantly higher odds (p<0.001) of skipping breakfast daily, drinking energy drinks daily, being drunk at least twice in their lifetime, risk of reduced psychological wellbeing, low life satisfaction, irritability, and problematic social media use and internet gaming compared with their peers without social jet lag (Table 2). The age category (11, 13 and 15 years) and the family socioeconomic status were not statistically significant covariates of the wellbeing indicators included in the regression analyses of sleep patterns in 2022.

DISCUSSION

Between 2014 and 2022, there was a sustained and significant increase in the prevalence of insufficient sleep, along with a decrease in sleep duration among Czech adolescents in all analysed age cohorts (11, 13 and 15 years.). Alarmingly, for the first time since the start of sleep monitoring, the average sleep duration on school days in 2022 dropped below the eight-hour threshold (7:57 minutes). This would place Czechia alongside Poland, Latvia and Estonia as the countries with the lowest sleep duration among 11–15-year-olds on school days, as found in previous cycles of the HBSC study (5). On school days, only 53% of boys and 48% of girls aged 11–15 years met the sleep duration recommendations (7, 8), a worse outcome than in the cohorts of 15-year-old adolescents from Finland, France, Hungary, Italy, Japan, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom (3, 4). This unfavourable ranking in recommended sleep duration on school days may be related to the early school start time in Czechia (8:00 a.m.), which is earlier than the typical school start time in Finland, France, South Africa, South Korea, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, as well as the inconsistent enforcement of bedtime rules in the families of adolescents. Delaying school start time by 25–60 minutes, so that classes begin no earlier than 8:30, could increase sleep duration on school days by 25–77 minutes (27), reduce late arrivals, and decrease instances of falling asleep during class (27, 28).

On non-school days, sleep duration among Czech adolescents was somewhat more favourable, likely reflecting an attempt to compensate for the sleep deficit accumulated on school days. Czech children obtained about 1.5 hours more sleep on non-school

days compared with school days, reaching an average of 9 hours and 31 minutes. This increase allowed 65% of boys and 67% of girls to meet the recommended sleep duration on weekends (7, 8). Nevertheless, even on non-school days, Czech adolescents slept for shorter periods than the cohort of 15-year-old adolescents from Finland, France, Hungary, Italy, Japan, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom (3, 4). However, when comparing sleep duration trends between school days and non-school days among Czech adolescents, we found a widening gap. A difference in sleep duration of more than 2 hours between non-school and school days (social jet lag) was evident in over a third of 11-year-old adolescents and in more than half of 13- and 15-year-olds. Such a gap may realistically contribute to significant health complaints or indicators of risky behaviour (9–11).

Late bedtimes on school and non-school days were a strong indicator of insufficient sleep duration, which has been significantly associated with difficulties falling asleep, unfavorable psychosocial and cardiometabolic health, and increased adiposity (1, 27). Although cardiometabolic health and adiposity were not monitored in our study, late bedtimes on school and non-school days were significantly associated with a wide range of indicators of poor wellbeing among Czech adolescents. For example, a close similarity between Czech adolescents and 13–15-year-olds from the UK was found in the excessive use of social media (14). UK adolescents aged 13–15 years with very high levels of social media use (over 5 hours per day) were characterised not only by significantly later bedtimes (after 23:00/0:00 on school/non-school days), but also longer time in bed, more frequent night waking and later wake-up times than adolescents with an average daily social media use of 1–3 hours (14). Similarly, 11–15-year-old adolescents from 18 European and North American countries with intense and problematic social media use reported later bedtimes, shorter sleep durations, and more pronounced social jet lag than similarly aged adolescents with normal daily social media activity (6). The increased likelihood of skipping breakfast among adolescents with late bedtimes seems to be a logical consequence of the difficulty of waking up and rushing to school. In addition, sleep-deprived adolescents are more often irritable and nervous and tend to consume energy drinks daily to a greater extent than their well-rested peers (28).

The social jet lag, the misalignment between biological and social timing determined by work or social obligations, can cause health complaints (9, 11) and problematic behaviours (9, 10) when experienced over a prolonged period. Similar to adolescents from Hong Kong (10) and northern European Russian adolescent girls (11), Czech adolescents aged 11–15 were also found to have a higher likelihood of mental health complaints if they experienced social jet lag greater than 2 hours than their peers with social jet lag of 0–30 minutes. The increased risk of more frequent breakfast skipping, irritability, and daily consumption of energy drinks in adolescents with social jet lag exceeding 2 hours can logically be explained by sleep deprivation and the resulting fatigue (28).

Study Limitations

The results and related wellbeing considerations must be interpreted in the light of the study's limitations. First, the HBSC study is a cross-sectional study conducted at four-year intervals, allowing associations to be identified but not permitting causal

relationships to be confirmed. Second, the data were self-reported and, although collected using standardized questions and protocols (16, 17), may be subject to recall bias or social desirability bias. In addition, sleep duration calculated from self-reported data by adolescents generally overestimates sleep duration, as falling asleep tends to occur later than the reported bedtime, leading to more conservative interpretations in our study. A more accurate determination of sleep duration and quality would be provided by device-measured sleep behaviour, which, however, has so far only been implemented in Czechia in smaller samples of children and their parents (29) or adolescents (30).

CONCLUSIONS

A significant decrease in sleep duration for Czech adolescents on school and non-school days was confirmed from 2014 to 2022. This held true independently of gender or age category. The most recent data from 2022 further imply there is a large proportion of adolescents facing consequences of social jet lag >2 hours. Regardless of the socioeconomic status of families and the adolescent age cohort, late bedtimes and social jet lag were significantly associated with poorer wellbeing indicators than adolescents with earlier daily bedtimes or adolescents without social jet lag. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight the importance of a comprehensive approach to addressing sleep difficulties in adolescence, which would include the family environment (e.g., the perceived role of parents in supporting adolescents, adolescents' adherence to bedtime rules) and take into account the school environment (e.g., the current quality of relationships with classmates, perceived attitude of teachers, and school-level demands).

Conflicts of Interest

None declared

Adherence to Ethical Standards

The Institutional Ethics Committee for Research of the Faculty of Physical Culture of Palacký University Olomouc approved the design of the cross-sectional study, the course of preparation and implementation of the research and the opt-out method of collecting parental consent and data processing for data collection in 2014 (2018 and 2022) in March 2013 under No. 17/2013 (on 4 March 2016 under No. 9/2016 and on 10 October 2020 under No. 65/2020).

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